

Development and Testing of a Multi-Layered Cherenkov Detector

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1 Introduction

Particle detection and particle identification (PID) are fundamental processes in experimental high-energy physics. An effective type of charged particle detector is the Cherenkov detector, which leverages the emission of Cherenkov radiation, a phenomenon discovered by Pavel Cherenkov in 1934 [1]. When a high-energy particle moves through a dielectric medium at a speed greater than the phase velocity of light, it emits Cherenkov radiation—a shockwave of light similar to a sonic boom. Arising from constructive interference between electromagnetic waves created from the particle’s motion, the radiation forms a cone, with an emission angle given by:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{c}{n v} \quad (1)$$

where θ is the Cherenkov angle, c is the speed of light, n is the refractive index, and v is particle speed.

Figure 1: For $v > \frac{c}{n}$, an electromagnetic “shockwave” appears, known as Cherenkov radiation, propagating at the Cherenkov angle. Characteristic cone-shaped Cherenkov radiation produced by a charged particle moving faster than the speed of light in a medium, where the angle of the cone depends on the medium’s refractive index.

After Cherenkov photons are detected, their emission angle can elucidate a particle’s speed. Combined with momentum data, this reveals a particle’s type. Ring-imaging Cherenkov (RICH) detectors map the light ring radius to precisely calculate the angle, while single-layer detectors use custom media such as low-density gases (e.g., tetrafluoromethane) for high-momentum, denser media (e.g., silica aerogel) for low-momentum particles [2]. However, single-layer designs often have drawbacks, limiting velocity detection ranges or requiring multiple specialized modules and photomultipliers.

To address these limitations, we developed a multi-layer Cherenkov detector comprising distinct dielectric media which we hope to test at the T9 beamline experimentally. This design enhances photon yield, detection efficiency, and particle discrimination through relative photon yield measurements while also enabling simultaneous identification of diverse particles across a broader momentum range compared to conventional single-layer detectors.

2 Why we want to go

Given the limited particle physics research opportunities within Singapore, we assembled, fully simulated and will soon test our own particle detector design on cosmic rays. However, cosmic ray tests alone provide incomplete results; the opportunity to experiment, test, and fully evaluate our detector design in CERN's T9 beamline would be an invaluable opportunity for us all as prospective scientists. We hope to bring our ideas to fruition, and we believe our design could yield meaningful findings towards improving particle detection.

3 Detector Design

The detector is designed with several factors in mind, including low cost (<\$300USD), reproducibility, and environmental sustainability, which determined many of the manufacturing processes and materials utilized.

3.1 Cylinder design

Figure 2: The assembled cylinder modules (SiPM not installed).

Our detector comprises three cylindrical segments interconnected via ConFlat (CF) flanges that can modularly attach, each containing a different medium for easy interchanging and assembly of media layers. The cylindrical structure comprises 3D-printed PLA filament coated with opaque black paint to block ambient light. The maximum particle travel distance before slowing down is ~ 30 cm [3], so the detector will test whether a single medium or different layered media are more effective within this constraint.

Thin Mylar-D film windows separate each 10 cm-long cylindrical segment. These films securely contain the liquids in each cell while minimally impeding the passage of particles and photons between layers. The interior walls are layered with aluminium foil to allow for diffuse reflection of photons, maximising the probability of photon detection at the photodetector.

Figure 3: a) interior, b) disassembled and c) cross-sectional view of the detector design.

3.2 Circuitry

Silicon multipliers (SiPM; AFBR-S4N33C013–3x3mm active area) are positioned toward the upper region within each cylinder, with two on each end (square perforations on the cylinder visible in Figure 3). Optical gel couples them to ensure proper light transmission. Through a DC-DC boost converter and operational amplifier (op-amp), the SiPMs provide readouts for individual photon intensity values [4].

Figure 4: 3D model of the SiPM and its readout.

3.3 Media

The selected media were chosen for their refractive indices, densities, and accessibility, and calculated using the simplified Lorentz-Lorenz mixing rules, with the following table listing the media along with their refractive indices and densities. Equation (2) is a volume-weighted average for density, and Equation (3) approximates a mixture's refractive index from the volume fractions of benzyl alcohol and water:

$$p_{\text{mix}} = \frac{p_1 V_1 + p_2 V_2}{V_1 + V_2} \quad (2)$$

$$n_{\text{mix}} \approx \phi_B n_B + \phi_W n_W \quad (3)$$

Medium	Refractive Index	Density (g/cm ³)
Water	1.33	1.000
Glycerin	1.46	1.261
Benzyl Alcohol	1.54	1.044
Water + Benzyl Alcohol*	1.44	1.020

Table 1: To compare Cherenkov yields in media of different refractive index but similar density since density affects photon emission [5], we prepared a 50/50 water-benzyl alcohol mixture that has an intermediate refractive index (1.44) while maintaining density close to water (1.02g/cm³).

4 Methodology & Criteria For Success

4.1 Beamline Setup

Figure 5: Abstracted schematic layout of beamline setup.

Block 1: Proton beam bombards target, generating a secondary beam containing particles we wish to test in our detector.

Block 2: Dipole magnets assist in selective beam steering, and a collimator refines beam focus and trajectory alignment.

Block 3: Input scintillator paddle provides initial particle tracking signal, followed by a delay wire chamber (DWC) tracker to reconstruct the particle’s 3D trajectory.

Block 4: CERN’s threshold Cherenkov detector provides a binary yes/no signal for particle threshold identification.

Block 5: Our detector.

Block 6: Second scintillation paddle operates in coincidence with the input scintillator, and additional DWC tracker enables full and accurate path reconstruction.

4.2 Proposed Day-By-Day Plan at CERN

Day	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Agenda	Calibration day, confirm dark count rates and trigger efficiency. Set up ROOT software	Testing with single media (water, glycerin, benzyl alcohol) at 1–15 GeV/c, with a 5 GeV/c step size. Focus on photon yield and efficiency.	Finish single medium testing.
Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7
Layered medium tests at the same momenta range, particularly focusing on pion/kaon discrimination using our model.	Repeat experiments with hybrid density-matched mixtures.	Repeat experiments with hybrid density-matched mixtures.	Data analysis and cross-checking with simulations.

Table 2: Tentative day-by-day plan at CERN.

4.3 Validation

To validate our detector, it is sought to consider three key aspects: yield, efficiency, and particle identification accuracy.

1. Yield

By using our op-amp, we can record the pulse waveforms of the photomultiplier output. From testing with cosmic rays, we can find the baseline noise of our detector. After subtracting the baseline, we will integrate over the pulse (voltage vs time) to obtain the total charge produced.

Figure 6: Standard SiPM Pulse [6] (area highlighted).

Calibration of our SiPM using single-photon dark noise spectra yields a conversion factor of $3.8 \times 10^{-13} \text{C}$ per photon. From this information, we will run a statistical test between the mean number of photons generated from our single-layer test versus the multi-layered test to determine statistical differences.

2. Efficiency

Trigger Efficiency

$$E_{\text{ff trigger}} = \frac{\text{Number of times photon(s) detected}}{\text{Number of scintillation triggers}} \quad (4)$$

Due to our device spanning over all momenta, the expected value for efficiency should be close to 100%.

Detection Efficiency

$$E_{\text{ff detection}} = \frac{\text{Number of particles detected}}{\text{Number of particles emitted by source}} \quad (5)$$

We have already shown how we calculate photon yield. We are also aware of the flux of the detector, from BL4S documentation:

Figure 7: T9 beamline beam momentum [8].

Therefore, we can write our detection efficiency as:

$$E_{\text{ff trigger}} = \frac{N_{\text{detected}}}{F \cdot A \cdot T \cdot Y_{\text{theory}}} \quad (6)$$

Where F is the flux, A is the SiPM detection area, T is the time interval, and Y is the expected photon amount, derived from the Frank-Tamm formula, which is elaborated on later:

$$\frac{d^2 N}{dx d\lambda} = \frac{2\pi\alpha}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2(\lambda)} \right) \quad (7)$$

Using the Frank-Tamm formula enables us to yield the amount of Cherenkov photons emitted as a function of particle speed, refractive index, and photon wavelength [7].

3. Particle Identification and Discrimination

Interestingly, we realized something about the methodology after we had already created the detector—a novel way to obtain information about the particles. Instead of setting a ring of photomultipliers as RICH detectors do, we can use the proportions of photon yield to make information about particles. Thereafter, we derived a model that inputs the data points and finds the velocity of the particle to much greater accuracy than single-layered detectors would by using the above Frank-Tamm formula.

We base our model on the Frank-Tamm formula, which yields the amount of Cherenkov radiation emitted as a function of particle speed, refractive index, and photon wavelength.

$$\frac{d^2 N}{dx d\lambda} = \frac{2\pi\alpha}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2(\lambda)} \right) \quad (1)$$

Integrating, we get:

$$N = \int_0^L \left(\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \frac{2\pi\alpha}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2(\lambda)} \right) d\lambda \right) dx \quad (2)$$

$$N = L \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \frac{2\pi\alpha}{\lambda^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2(\lambda)} \right) d\lambda \quad (3)$$

Note that since all our photomultipliers have the same spectral responses (detection rates at different wavelengths), and dispersionary effects are very minor (a few percent at most), we can take the refractive index to be a constant. Then, we can integrate at get:

$$N = L 2\pi\alpha \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_1} - \frac{1}{\lambda_2}\right) \quad (4)$$

Since we are only concerned with the ratio of the N 's (scaling by other values or by constants will not affect the m value, only shifting the graph), we can factor out the constants and get:

$$N \propto c \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$N \propto \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta^2 n^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

This essentially shows the relationship between relative photon yield, speed, and refractive index. Our model works by taking our different photon yield values (the mean of each of the two Sipms in each cylinder), and plotting it with the respective refractive index. Then, we can easily fit the above equation to find beta.

$$y = 1 - \frac{m}{x^2} \quad (7)$$

Where:

$$y = N, \quad m = \frac{1}{\beta^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad x^2 = n^2 \text{ (i.e., } x = n\text{)}.$$

With the velocity and the known energies, we can discriminate between particles like pions and kaons. By comparing with the flux, we can see how accurate we were.

Example:

For the following relative measurements of photon yield:

SiPM 1	SiPM 1	SiPM 1	SiPM 1	SiPM 1	SiPM 1
0.36	0.38	0.47	0.51	0.50	0.56
Refractive Index 1		Refractive Index 2		Refractive Index 3	
1.33		1.47		1.54	

We fit the line:

Find Beta:

We have m has 1.111. Therefore, beta must be 0.9462, or $v = 283,645,00$ m/s. This is a relatively untested method, and it offers advantages in detection capabilities (more accurate), as well as cost and simplicity in design. With beta equal to 0.9462 and the beam's energy to be 10 GeV, we use:

$$E = \gamma mc^2 \quad (8)$$

where in this case, is 3.09, we identify the rest mass to be 3.24 GeV. With these properties, we can identify the particle to be some heavy meson. With these values, the closest particle is a J/ψ meson.

Our overall goal is to test this model using our detector on the T9 beamline, achieve a $> 90\%$ discrimination between pions and kaons in layered media at 1-15 GeV/c, and test its robustness in comparison to the beamline flux.

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6 Appendix: Supplementary Figures

6.1 Detector In Action: Cosmic Rays

Figure 8: Output of a SiPM Module in the detector (medium: water)

Figure 10 shows the output of our SiPM when we tested it by detecting cosmic rays (high speed muons). The peaks represent Cherenkov photon detection, signifying muon detection.

6.2 Calculated Cherenkov Threshold Table for Different Media

Medium	Proton	Pion (π^\pm)	Kaon (K^\pm)	Muons (μ^\pm)	Electron/Positron
Water	484.86	72.12	255.11	54.60	0.264
Glycerin	349.49	51.99	183.89	39.36	0.190
Benzyl Alcohol	295.50	43.96	155.48	33.28	0.161
Water + Benzyl Alcohol	365.71	54.40	192.42	41.18	0.199

Table 3: Cherenkov threshold kinetic energy (MeV) for various particles in different media.

6.3 GEANT4 Simulation

Figure 9: Simulation of detector design and spatial distribution of Cherenkov photons

A cylindrical detector contains three dielectric layers: distilled water, glycerin, and benzyl alcohol. Cosmic muons (μ^- , red) enter at ~ 4 GeV, producing Cherenkov photons (γ , green) detected by wall-mounted SiPMs. Photon positions are recorded, generating a 3D scatter plot of detection coordinates on the detector's surface. The above is a simulation we ran on these muons, clearly showing the detection spikes which match that of cosmic rays.

6.4 Circuit and wiring diagram of the detector

Figure 10: Schematic of the SiPM biasing and readout circuit

7 Citations

1. Roberts, A.A., et al. “The Discovery of the Cherenkov Radiation.” Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, North-Holland, 5 July 2008, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0168900208009297>.
2. Ratcliff, Blair N. “Imaging Rings in Ring Imaging Cherenkov Counters.” INSPIRE, Sept. 2002, <https://inspirehep.net/>.
3. A. Abed Abud, B. Abi, R. Acciarri, M. A. Acero, M. R. Adames, et al. “The hypothetical track-length fitting algorithm for energy measurement in liquid argon TPCs”, Arxiv, Oct. 1 2024, <https://arxiv.org/html/2409.18288v2>.
4. “Farnell.” BROADCOM®️, <https://www.farnell.com/datasheets/1503896.pdf>.
5. Meng, Xianming. “A Photon Density Theory Explaining Experiments on High-Order Doppler Effect.” International Journal of Physics, Science and Education Publishing, 6 Dec. 2021, <https://pubs.sciepub.com/ijp/9/6/6/index.html>.
6. Introduction to the Silicon Photomultiplier (SiPM) And9770/d, <https://www.onsemi.com/pub/Collateral/AND9770-D.PDF>.
7. G N Afanasiev, et al. “On Tamm’s Problem in the Vavilov-Cherenkov Radiation Theory.” Nuclear Theory, <https://arxiv.org/list/nucl-th/recent>.
8. Beam and Detectors - Beamline for Schools (BL4S), https://beamline-for-schools.web.cern.ch/sites/default/files/Beams_Detectors_BL4S2024.pdf.